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People Who Remain Poor Even After Social Transfers in Europe

They grew 2.09% between 2010 and 2021

The Eurostat calculates the value of people who remain poor even after social transfer. That is, people who have an available income below 60% of the available income calculated at national level even after having collected social transfers.

Ranking of countries by the value of people who remain poor even after social transfers in 2021. Latvia is in the first place for the value of people who remain poor even after social transfers with an amount equal to 23.4%, followed by Romania with an amount of 22.6% and from Bulgaria with an amount of 22.1%. In the middle of the standings there are Germany with an amount of 16%, followed by Sweden with an amount of 15.7%, and from Poland with an amount of 14.8%. Slovenia closes the ranking with an amount of 11.7%, followed by Finland with an amount of 10.8% and by the Czech Republic with an amount of 8.6%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of people who remain poor even after social transfers between 2010 and 2021. The Netherlands is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of people who remain poor even after the social transfers between the 2010 and 2021 with an amount equal to 39.81% equal to an amount of 4.10, followed by Estonia with an amount of 30.38% equal to an amount of 4.80 units, and the Luxembourg with an amount of 24.83% equal to an amount of 3.60 units. In the middle of the standings there are Portugal with an amount of 2.79% equal to an amount of 0.50 units, from Germany with an amount of 2.56% equal to an amount of 0.40 units, and from Slovakia with a amount of 2.50% equal to an amount of 0.30 units. Ireland closes the ranking with an amount of -15.13% equal to an amount of -2.30 unit, followed by Poland with an amount of -15.91% equal to an amount of -2.80 units and from the Finland with a value of -17.56% equal to an amount of -2.30 units. On average between 2010 and 2021 the value of people who remain poor even after social transfers grew by 2.09% equal to an amount of 0.31 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The clusterization with the K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is analyzed below. The analysis shows the presence of three Clusters. The Clusters are thus established or:

- Cluster 1: Germany, Malta, Sweden, Poland, Luxembourg, Cyprus, Belgium, Ireland, Sweden, Portugal, Austria;
- Cluster 2: Spain, Bulgaria, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Italy, Greece, Estonia, Croatia;
- Cluster 3: Slovakia, Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, Hungary.

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From the point of view of the median it is possible to identify the following Clusters or: $C2 = 20.6 > C1 = 14.8 > C3 = 12.3$. From a geographical point of view, it is possible to verify the dominance of Eastern and southern European countries, followed by European countries in the center and the North.

Network Analysis with the use of Euclidean distance. An analysis is presented below using Network Analysis through the use of the Euclidean distance. Three network structures are identified of which three are simplified and two are complex. In particular, the following connections exist or:

- Finland has a connection with Denmark for a value of 0.52 units, and with Slovakia for an amount of 0.46 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Finland for a value of 0.52 units, and with Slovakia for a value of 0.52 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Finland for an amount of 0.46 units and with Denmark equal to an amount of 0.52 units. +
- The following connections are also detected:
- Luxembourg has a connection with Sweden for an amount of 0.54 units, with mortar for an amount of 0.57 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.54 units, with mortar for an amount of 0.3 units, and with Germany for an amount of 0.56 units;
- Malta has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.57 units, with Germany for an amount of 0.56 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.3 units;
- Germany has a connection with Malta for an amount of 0.56 units, and with Sweden for an amount of 0.56 units.

There are also the following simplified connections or:

- Belgium and Cyprus have a connection for an amount of 0.47 units;
- Hungary and Slovenia have a connection for an amount of 0.32 units;
- Austria and France have a connection of 0.48 units.

Conclusions. The number of poor people who remain such even after obtaining social transfers grew in Europe between 2010 and 2021 on average of an amount of 2.09%. This growth also took place in countries rich from the point of view of pro-capita income such as the Netherlands and Luxembourg for example. This growth highlights the insufficiency of income support measures and contrasting poverty that are not adequate to allow a considerable part of the population to get out of poverty. In a world where agriculture, buildings and manufacture have lost the ability to produce jobs, and where the manifest services sector also of fragility following artificial intelligence applications, countries must develop Support policies the income concerning both the unemployed and employed. In fact, poverty is no longer a phenomenon that concerns unemployed people. On the contrary, poverty is increasingly a condition that characterizes the position of the workers, or the so-called working poors, which begin to become many also in the service sector, characterized by intermittence, precariousness, and income insufficiency. It follows that the idea of universal income is no longer a utopian dimension or connected to the postmodernist event of communist economic policies, but rather a necessity to allow the population to strengthen those consumption of goods and services that constitute 80-85% of the GDP of high-income countries.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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